

cocyber

Brand Guidelines

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Brand Strategy

vision

To create a robust, resilient, and interconnected European cybersecurity ecosystem that fosters innovation, enhances digital capabilities, and ensures strategic autonomy by harmonizing civilian and defence efforts.

establish a robust and resilient European cybersecurity ecosystem that seamlessly integrates both civilian and defence spheres. We aim to foster an environment that encourages innovation, enhances digital capabilities, and ensures strategic autonomy. This ecosystem will not only be a platform for collaboration and technology transfer but also a catalyst for policy harmonisation and stakeholder engagement.

In this interconnected ecosystem, advancements in one sphere will directly benefit the other, leading to a more secure and responsive cybersecurity landscape across Europe.

By bridging the gap between civilian and defence efforts, we envision a future where Europe leads the global discourse in cybersecurity.

COcyber is dedicated to facilitating coordination and support in the realm of cybersecurity across the European Union. Recognising the inherent interdependencies between civilian and defence cybersecurity efforts, we aim to create a platform that encourages information-sharing and technology transfer. Our mission is to ensure that advancements in one sphere resonate in the other, thereby strengthening the overall European cybersecurity landscape.

In our pursuit of policy harmonisation, we conduct comprehensive analyses of the cybersecurity technology sector, addressing political, economic, social, technological, legal, and environmental factors (PESTEL). The insights derived from these analyses inform our policy recommendations, optimising transnational cybersecurity civil-defence cooperation and advancing Europe's position in international cybersecurity discourse.

mission

Target Audience

Target persona 1

Gender: Male

Age: 25-40

Profession: Cybersecurity researcher or professional in a tech startup or research institution

Education: Degree in Computer Science, Information Technology, Cybersecurity

Project: A collaborative project that involves the development of an innovative cybersecurity solution. This could be a new encryption algorithm, a secure communication protocol, or a novel intrusion detection system. The project would involve extensive research and development, testing and validation, and finally, technology transfer to relevant civilian and defence entities. The innovator would have the opportunity to work with a diverse team of experts, gain exposure to cutting-edge cybersecurity technologies, and make a significant contribution to enhancing Europe's cybersecurity landscape.

Target persona 2

Gender: Female

Age: 35-60

Profession: Government official or intergovernmental organization representative dealing with cybersecurity policies

Education: Degree in Political Science, International Relations, Law, Cybersecurity

Project: A policy-oriented project that involves conducting a comprehensive PESTEL analysis of the cybersecurity technology sector. The project would aim to identify key trends, challenges, and opportunities in the sector, and how these factors influence cybersecurity policies at the national, European, and international levels. Based on this analysis, the project would then develop policy recommendations to optimize transnational cybersecurity civil-defence cooperation. The policy maker would play a crucial role in this project, leveraging their expertise to guide the analysis and shape the policy recommendations.

Personality

This archetype represents COcyber's commitment to exploring new frontiers in cybersecurity. As an explorer, COcyber is always on the lookout for innovative ideas and technologies that can enhance the cybersecurity landscape.

This archetype embodies the project's spirit of adventure and discovery, its willingness to take risks and push boundaries, and its commitment to learning and growth.

The Explorer is driven by curiosity and a desire to make a difference, qualities that resonate with COcyber's mission of fostering innovation and building capacity in the cybersecurity sector.

This archetype reflects COcyber's role as a knowledgeable guide in the realm of cybersecurity. As a sage, COcyber possesses deep understanding and insight into the complexities of cybersecurity, and uses this knowledge to inform and enlighten others.

This archetype embodies the project's commitment to wisdom, truth, and clarity.

The Sage seeks to understand the world and help others do the same, qualities that align with COcyber's mission of conducting comprehensive analyses and informing policy recommendations.

A person wearing a dark shirt and jeans is working on a wooden project in a workshop. The scene is lit with a blue and green glow. A large, glowing green circle is centered over the text 'The Creator'.

The Creator

This archetype embodies COcyber's ambition to create a robust and resilient cybersecurity ecosystem within the EU. As a creator, COcyber is driven by the desire to bring ideas to life, to build and construct, to design and innovate.

This archetype represents the project's creative spirit, its ability to see potential where others do not, and its commitment to making a lasting impact.

The Creator is motivated by the desire to create something of enduring value, a quality that resonates with COcyber's vision of establishing a robust and interconnected European cybersecurity ecosystem.

Visual Tools

Logo

Main version

Logo

Secondary version

Logo

Monochromatic version

How to use small size logo Uses the small version of the logo for applications below **160px/42mm in height**

Logo

Main version

Logo

Secondary version

Logo

Monochromatic version

How to use small size logo Uses the small version of the logo for applications below **60px/16mm in height**

Colors

Introduction to the selected color palette for a brand

The brand's color scheme includes the primary, secondary, accent (or exception to use in case of an error), and neutral colors such as white or black.

The primary color is the most dominant and recognizable color of the brand, followed by the secondary colors that complement and contrast with the primary color. The secondary colors are ordered according to the priority indicated in the diagram on the right, where the top color has higher priority than the bottom color. Refer to the diagram on the right for specific colors and their contrast ratio*

*Source:

www.w3.org/TR/WCAG20/#visual-audio-contrast

Yale Blue PRIMARY

#0B4A89

R11 G74 B137

C99 M73 Y16 K3

Contrast Ratio

8.54:1 AAA

Russian Green SECONDARY

#5DA359

R93 G163 B89

C68 M13 Y80 K1

Contrast Ratio

5.50:1 AA

Banana Yellow SECONDARY

#FFE53B

R255 G229 B59

C3 M5 Y82 K0

Contrast Ratio

13.26:1 AAA

Green-Yellow ACCENT

#AFFC29

R175 G252 B41

C40 M0 Y100 K0

Contrast Ratio

13.47:1 AAA

Lotion NEUTRAL

#FAFAFA

R250 G250 B250

C2 M2 Y2 K0

Contrast Ratio

16.15:1 AAA

Eerie Black NEUTRAL

#1D1D1D

R29 G29 B29

C0 M0 Y0 K90

Contrast Ratio

16.15:1 AAA

Colors

Gradient table

Specification of the gradient table

The gradient table indicates which neutral color (black or white) to use for writing text based on the percentage of opacity.

Refer to the adjacent table for more information.

Typography

Title

The font displayed is intended for use only in titles and subtitles.
DOWNLOAD FONT: <https://fonts.google.com/specimen/DM%20Sans>

Aa

Titles

DM Sans Bold Apply with kerning at -100

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii
Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr
Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz

0123456789

[(@#%\$^&)]" < > ! ?

Typography

Paragraph

The font displayed is intended for use only in titles and subtitles.

DOWNLOAD FONT: <https://fonts.google.com/specimen/DM%20Sans>

AaBb

DM Sans Regular

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk
Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu
Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz

0123456789

[(@#%\$^&)]" < > ! ?

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Texture

How to use

The texture must be applied by **alternating the symbols**, spacing them 90° apart.
Finally, **rotate the overall composition by 15°**

Elements

Texture assemble

15°

Full texture

Mockups

Title Example

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed diam nonummy nibh euismod tincidunt ut laoreet dolore magna aliquam erat volutpat.

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Title Example

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Title Example

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Ut wisi enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exerci tation ullamcorper suscipit lobortis nisl ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. accumsan et iusto odio dignissim.

Title Example

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed diam nonummy nibh euismod tincidunt ut laoreet dolore magna aliquam erat volutpat. Ut wisi enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exerci tation ullamcorper suscipit lobortis nisl ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis autem vel eum iriure dolor in hendrerit in vulputate velit esse molestie consequat, vel illum dolore eu feugiat nulla facilisis at vero eros et accumsan et iusto odio dignissim qui blandit praesent luptatum zzril delenit augue dui dolore te feugait nulla facilisi.

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